

Kinetics of the Transformation of Charge Transfer Complexes of Chloranil with Alicyclic n-Donors

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The transformation of charge transfer complexes of chloranil with three alicyclic secondary amines, piperidine, piperazine and morpholine, leading to the formation of substitution products is investigated spectroscopically and kinetically. Based on the results a plausible mechanism is proposed through outer and inner complexes as intermediates, the conversion of outer to inner complex being the rate determining step.

THE interaction of chloranil (2,3,5,6-tetrachloro-1,4-benzoquinone) with aromatic and aliphatic amines is reported to form charge transfer (CT) complexes¹⁻⁴. It appears from the literature⁵⁻⁸ that there exist different types of intermediates in the electron donor-acceptor interactions, but the existence depends on the nature of the donor and the conditions employed. We have reported earlier our studies on the formation of CT complexes of chloranil with piperidine, piperazine and morpholine as n-donors^{9,10}. Our investigations showed that the CT complexes of bromanil transform to disubstituted products in solution with excess concentrations of the donors⁹. Chloranil being a more familiar quinone, the studies are further extended and the results are reported here.

Experimental

Chloranil (E. Merck) was recrystallised twice from acetone. All the three donor compounds were obtained from Fluka, and were purified as reported earlier. Chloroform (Glaxo, spectroscopy grade) was further purified¹¹. Carbon tetrachloride and dichloromethane were also sufficiently pure. Stock solutions of 10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ were prepared and diluted as needed.

A CZ Spekol spectrophotometer was used for absorption measurements with optically matched 1 cm Corex cells, while time-dependent absorption spectra for the transformation of CT complex to the final product were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP-700 A UV-VIS spectrophotometer. A Toshniwal GL-15 constant temperature bath was used. Beckman IR-12 and Bruker FT-400 MHz nmr spectrometers were used for the analysis of final products.

Isolation of final products: Chloranil (~0.3 g) in chloroform was treated with four times excess of the donor, and the mixture was refluxed for almost completion of the reaction as indicated by tlc. The unreacted donor was separated by fractionation on

a column containing silica gel. n-Hexane-benzene mixture (1:1 by volume) was used as eluant. The solid products were isolated by evaporating the solvent and were dried.

Kinetic measurements: Chloranil and donor (always about 100-fold excess) were mixed with chloroform. The kinetics were followed for the transformation of CT complex by measuring the decrease in the absorbance (Table 1) and also by measuring the increase in the absorbance of the product. Temperature was maintained constant at 304 ± 0.2 K by circulating water. The pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from the gradients of the plots of $\log(A_{\infty} - A_t)$ vs time, where A_{∞} is the absorbance at the time of maximum absorbance and A_t at time t . Variation in the dielectric constants was made using mixtures of chloroform with carbon tetrachloride or dichloromethane.

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION MAXIMA OF CT COMPLEX AND PRODUCTS OF CHLORANIL

Donor	Absorption maxima, nm	
	CT Complex*	Product
Piperidine	578	449
Piperazine	575	448
Morpholine	570	442

*From Ref. 9.

Results and Discussion

Spectroscopic studies: The composition of the CT complexes of chloranil with these donors is found⁹ to be 1:1 and the complexes are in equilibrium with the components¹⁰. The complexes are stable in excess concentrations of chloranil, but transforms to different absorption species with excess concentrations of the donors, analogous to that of bromanil⁹. The 292 nm absorption maximum due to chloranil slowly disappears with the 449 nm peak simultaneously appearing and finally remains

stable. However, the 578 nm peak, which is due to the CT complex appears and disappears, finally culminating in the 449 nm absorption maximum.

The transformed species in solution and the solid isolated products when dissolved in chloroform have the same band maxima (Table 1), indicating that the isolated products and the species in solution are one and the same. The infrared frequencies of the products are summarised in Table 2. The results indicate that NH group of the donor moiety in the case of piperidine and morpholine is absent in the product. However, in the case of piperazine, the

TABLE 4—IR DATA OF PRODUCTS AND ASSIGNMENTS

ν (in cm^{-1}) of the product with			Assignment/ Functional group
Piperidine	Piperazine	Morpholine	
—	3 200	—	Aliph N—H
2 940	2 910	2 970	Aliph C—H
2 850	2 770	2 880	
1 645	1 655	1 650	C=O
1 552	1 565	1 570	C=O
1 400	1 405	1 405	C—O
1 355	1 360	1 360	C—O
1 340	1 340	1 335	
1 285	1 285	1 285	Ar—N—C
—	—	1 175	C—O—C
1 085	1 095	1 075	O—Cl
1 045	1 045	1 055	C—O—C
780	740	740	
—	—	625	C—O—C

second NH group persists. Further, the presence of the carbonyl frequency in all the products indicates that the product is not of the Schiff type reaction and can be a substitution one. A positive silver chloride test for the aqueous extract of the reaction mixture with silver nitrate for the products involving all the three donors confirms the substitution reaction^{1,2}.

The absence of NH group of the donor moiety of the product (except in case of piperazine) is also evidenced from the results of proton nmr data (Table 3). The integration ratios of the different proton resonance signals of the product do support the substitution reaction^{1,2}. The data on the elemental analysis (Table 4) indicate the degree of substitution as 2 and thus it is evident that chloranil forms disubstitution products with all the three donors.

Kinetic results : In excess concentrations of the donor, the CT complex formation is reasonably fast. The rate of the CT complex formation is observed^{1,2} to be first order with respect to the donor as well as

TABLE 3—PROTON NMR RESULTS OF PRODUCTS

Product with	δ^*			Integration ratio
	on N	on α O to N	on β, γ O to N	
Piperidine	Absent	3.49	1.55	2 : 8
Piperazine	1.65	2.52	2.42	1 : 4 : 4
Morpholine	Absent	3.81	3.58	1 : 1

*TMS as internal standard.

TABLE 4—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS DATA

Product with	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
	C	H	N
Piperidine	56.8 (55.9)	5.81 (5.88)	8.10 (8.16)
Piperazine	48.1 (48.7)	5.17 (5.25)	15.9 (16.2)
Morpholine	49.0 (48.4)	4.74 (4.65)	8.06 (8.07)

the acceptor. The rate is observed to be first order with respect to the CT complex as well as the donor in the case of product formation (Table 5) also and the total order is two. Similar results are observed by following the transformation of the CT complex.

TABLE 5—KINETIC RESULTS ON FORMATION OF PRODUCTS

[Chloranil] $\times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3}	[Donor] $\times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3}	ϵ	k' $\times 10^3$ s $^{-1}$	k'' $\times 10$ dm 3 mol $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$
with Piperidine				
3.00	1.41	4.8	1.36	—
4.00	1.41	4.8	1.37	—
6.00	1.41	4.8	1.37	—
5.00	1.41	4.8	1.39	9.87
5.00	1.18	4.8	1.19	9.64
5.00	1.65	4.8	1.60	9.71
5.00	1.63	4.8	1.81	9.79
4.00	1.70	3.3	—	4.70
4.00	1.70	6.4	—	13.50
4.00	1.70	8.0	—	18.10
with Piperazine				
2.00	3.65	4.8	0.97	—
4.00	3.65	4.8	1.02	—
6.00	3.65	4.8	1.01	—
8.00	3.65	4.8	1.06	2.95
8.00	4.26	4.8	1.26	2.96
8.00	5.47	4.8	1.63	2.98
8.00	6.03	4.8	1.82	3.01
6.00	3.69	3.4	—	1.90
6.00	3.69	6.4	—	5.30
6.00	3.69	7.5	—	7.01
with Morpholine				
3.00	39.7	4.8	0.79	—
4.00	39.7	4.8	0.78	—
5.00	39.7	4.8	0.79	—
6.00	39.7	4.8	0.79	0.20
6.00	19.9	4.8	0.98	0.19
6.00	29.3	4.8	0.57	0.19
6.00	59.5	4.8	1.19	0.20
5.00	53.2	3.6	—	0.17
5.00	53.2	6.4	—	0.38
5.00	53.2	7.5	—	0.55

The specific rate constants for the decomposition of the CT complexes of chloranil with piperidine, piperazine and morpholine are 0.398, 0.134 and 0.011 dm 3 mol $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$, respectively. These values do differ considerably with those of the product formation (Table 5). This supports the view that formation of the product is not directly from the CT complex but through an intermediate, the conversion of the CT complex to the intermediate being the rate determining step. Initial quadratic

behaviour is observed when the concentration of the product is plotted against time. This behaviour is similar to that observed earlier with other quinones^{9,11} and indicates that there exists an intermediate between CT complex and the final product. The intermediate could be an inner complex type as suggested by Rappoport¹⁴ and Nagakura⁸. No spectral evidence could, however, be obtained for this intermediate, which may be due to its transitory existence.

In view of the above results the following mechanism may be proposed for the molecular interaction between chloranil and alicyclic n-donors.

The results on the variation of the dielectric constant indicate that the rate of the formation of the product is dependent on the dielectric constant of the solvent medium (Table 5), the higher the dielectric constant the greater is the reaction rate of product formation. The specific rate constants listed in Table 5 are in the order, piperidine > piperazine > morpholine, which indicates the reactivity of the bases. This behaviour is consistent with the pK_a values of the donors and the trend is the same as with bromanil⁹.

Although the spectroscopic investigations do not indicate the difference in the accepting ability of

chloranil and bromanil, the present kinetic results suggest that the rates of EDA interactions of chloranil are relatively lower than those of bromanil.

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